

BALLAST IMPACT EFFECT ON FATIGUE RESISTANCE OF COMPOSITE BASED CARBODYSHELLS IN RAILWAYS

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with integrating ballast impact influence in fatigue assessment for carbodyshell design. Finite element method is applied to ballast impact analysis by using ABAQUS/Explicit. Many impact parameters are integrated in the numerical model, such as: impactor shape, mass, velocity; material properties of composite plate and its stacking sequences; etc. Impact behaviour, resistance of undamaged specimens and residual resistance of damaged specimens under 4 point bending are simulated, respectively. Then lifetime of damaged specimens can be estimated according to the S-N curve of undamaged one, with the residual strength. A safety factor can be defined as ratio of strength / residual strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

The transportation industry has for a long time been engaged in the application of new lightweight (composite) materials for primary structural design in an effort to develop more energy efficient structures to meet low emissions targets [1, 2].

Ballast impact problems are quite frequently encountered by rolling stock manufacturers and this type of impact cannot be avoided. These are the reasons why the standards and regulations are needed to limit or avoid disastrous consequences for the rolling stock structures.

The ballast impact represents the specific phenomena (Fig. 1). The mass of ballast is nearly 0.06 kg which is the mass average of a piece of ballast. More details of ballast description are reported in [3]. The causes of ballast impact are diverse: the sudden change of the train speed, the vibrations induced by the rolling of the train, etc. The most one frequently found in literature is due to snowfall or ice, pasted under the train car during its working. Snow or pieces of ice formed under the body of the train gaining weight over time and fall on the ballast road to cause the detachment of ballast components. Some ballast components can reach sufficient heights to damage the structure of the train (Fig. 2). The velocity of ballast impact is almost the same as the train speed.

The aim of this study is to integrate ballast impact influence in fatigue assessment for carbodyshell design. Finite element method is applied to ballast impact analysis by using ABAQUS/Explicit. Many impact parameters are integrated in the numerical model, such as: impactor shape, mass, velocity; material properties of composite plate and its stacking sequences; etc. Based on a literature review, it is possible to predict fatigue lifetimes of impact damaged composites from knowledge of the residual strength of the impact damaged composite and the S-N curve for the undamaged material. After simulating impact behaviour and residual resistance of damaged specimens under 4 point bending, a safety factor can be defined as ratio of strength / residual strength.

Figure 1: Type of ballast

Figure 2: Principle of ballast impact

2 NUMERICAL MODELLING OF IMPACT

In order to predict the ballast impact influence, a finite element (FE) model that is carefully developed can accurately predict in relatively short time the complex internal damage pattern that is formed in composite laminates when subjected to impact loading. A desirable approach could be able to avoid the considerably expensive and time consuming process of performing the physical experiment. This section, briefly describes the impact modeling process of composite structures.

According to literature review, ABAQUS is more frequently used for finite element analysis of impact [4-18]. As a consequence, this code is chosen for this study. The following discussions will be concentrated on ABAQUS.

2.1 Solution method

In order to model a dynamic phenomenon like impact by ABAQUS, it is possible to solve the problems with an explicit or implicit algorithm available in ABAQUS. In an explicit scheme, the analysis cost rises only linearly with problem size, whereas the cost of solving the nonlinear equations associated with implicit integration rises more rapidly than linearly with problem size. Therefore, ABAQUS/Explicit is attractive.

2.2 Impactor modelling

It is possible to model the impactor in three different methods:

- 1: Impactor could be assumed as a rigid body and no property is assigned which means that the impactor is with infinite rigidity (which is referred as fully rigid),
- 2: Impactor could be assumed as a rigid body, but with property assigned which means that the impactor is with real rigidity,
- 3: It is also possible to consider the impactor as a rigid deformable body with property assigned.

In conclusion, the impactor can be modeled as an elastic solid but in general it is considered as a rigid body [4-14]. This assumption is quite realistic because of negligible deformation of the projectile.

2.3 Interface modelling

According to the capabilities offered by the ABAQUS/Explicit, different alternatives for interface modeling can be considered [15], see Fig. 3.

The case depicted in Fig. 3a is the most common way to model the composite plate. It consists of modeling the cohesive connections using continuum elements (zero or non-zero thickness), and the in-plane size of the mesh of all layers is defined equal, including composite plies and cohesive layers. Therefore, the nodes of each layer are shared with the neighboring layers. A drawback of using cohesive elements is that it degrades the runtime analysis because their thickness is small or equal to zero, which results in small stable time increments.

Figure 3: Interface modeling: (a) using cohesive elements and a regular mesh, (b) using cohesive elements and tie constraints, or (c) using surface-based cohesive interactions. [15]

2.4 Type of elements

According to ABAQUS, conventional shell, continuum shell and solid elements are available options in the modelling of the composite structures. In addition, continuum shell composite layups take into account double-sided contact and thickness changes, which provides more accurate contact modelling than conventional shell composite layups [19].

SC8R element is classified in the category of continuum shell elements. This element is an eight-node continuum shell element and has three degrees of freedom per each node (only displacement degrees of freedom). After a comparison, Khalili et al. [4] have concluded that SC8R is a more suitable element for modelling quasi-static as well as dynamic impact problems on both thin and thick composite structures. So, SC8R has been chosen for simulating composite laminates.

The separation of adjacent plies due to normal or shear loads, referred to as delamination, absorbs impact energy and decreases the laminate stiffness and therefore needs to be covered by the model as well. Because delamination cannot be represented inside the continuum shell elements, the laminate was divided into a certain number of sublaminates with cohesive elements in-between, which can fail during the simulation according to a specified failure law. The cohesive elements of type COH3D8 were modelled with zero initial thickness so that the total laminate thickness is not influenced by the additional element layers [16].

2.5 Damage model

- Onset and evolution of intra-laminar damages

For composite materials, the damage initiation criteria are based on the Hashin's theory, which is based separately on the different intra-laminar failure modes (Table 1, where α is a coefficient, which allows taking in account the shear stress contribution in the fibre tensile failure mode).

Hashin's failure criteria	
$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_t}\right)^2 + \alpha\left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_t}\right)^2 = 1$	Fiber tensile failure
$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_c}\right)^2 = 1$	Fiber compressive failure
$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_t}\right)^2 = 1$	Matrix tensile failure
$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{2S_t}\right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{Y_t}{2S_t}\right)^2 - 1\right]\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_t}\right)^2 = 1$	Matrix compressive failure

Table 1: Hashin's failure criteria

Four different modes of failure have been considered: fiber rupture in tension and compression and matrix cracking under transverse tension and compression. Both their onset and evolution can be modelled respectively using Hashin's criteria.

- Onset and evolution of inter-laminar damages

In order to simulate inter-laminar damages (delaminations), the maxs damage criterion (called "MAXS DAMAGE") is adopted in the first phase of the traction–separation law. Damage is assumed to initiate when the maximum nominal stress ratio (as defined in Eq. 1) reaches a value of one. In addition, the quadratic nominal stress criterion (QUADS) is also applicable: this criterion is able to connect the stresses in all different directions and its expression is presented in Eq. 2.

$$\max \left\{ \left(\frac{\sigma_n}{N_{max}} \right), \left(\frac{\sigma_t}{T_{max}} \right), \left(\frac{\sigma_s}{S_{max}} \right) \right\} = 1 \quad (1)$$

Where: N_{max} is the nominal stress in the pure normal mode, T_{max} is the nominal stress in the first shear direction and S_{max} is the nominal stress in the second shear direction, respectively.

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_n}{N_{max}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_t}{T_{max}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_s}{S_{max}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

In particular, ABAQUS allows choosing either a linear or an exponential softening behaviour during the evolution phase. Frequently, a linear softening behaviour could be chosen. Also, during this phase, the dependence of the fracture energy on the mixed mode can be defined based on a power law fracture criterion or "Benzeggagh-Kenane BK" criterion [20].

The power law criterion states that failure under mixed-mode condition is governed by Eq. 3:

$$\left\{ \frac{G_n}{G_n^c} \right\}^\alpha + \left\{ \frac{G_s}{G_s^c} \right\}^\alpha + \left\{ \frac{G_t}{G_t^c} \right\}^\alpha = 1 \quad (3)$$

Where G_n^c ; G_s^c ; and G_t^c are the critical fracture energies required that cause failure in the normal, the first and the second shear directions, respectively.

The "Benzeggagh–Kenane BK" criterion is presented with Eq. 4:

$$G_{Ic} + (G_{IIc} - G_{Ic}) \left(\frac{G_{SHEAR}}{G_T} \right)^\eta = G_{TC} \quad (4)$$

Where $G_{j\epsilon}$ is the critical Energy Release Rate associated to the fracture mode j ($G_{I\epsilon}$ Normal mode fracture energy; $G_{II\epsilon}$ Shear mode fracture energy first direction; $G_{III\epsilon}$ Shear mode fracture energy second direction); η is an experimental parameter generally varying in a range between 1 and 1.6.

3 PROPOSED APPROACH FOR IMPACT INFLUENCE ASSESSMENT

In general, impact damaged components, particularly when the damage can barely be detected by the naked eye, will continue to fulfill their function unless the damage obviously affects the safety of the structure or there is some other failure criterion such as aesthetic considerations. In all cases it is important to be able to predict the response to the prevailing loading conditions and understand the damage development in the impacted component during the remainder of its service life.

Tong and Isaac [21, 22] have studied fatigue behavior on impacted specimens made of glass fiber and hemsps fiber. According to their results, it can be concluded that the fatigue lives of composites after impact damage decrease due to degradation in the strength of the composites. However, when fatigue strength data are normalized with respect to their respective residual strengths, the effect of impact damage on fatigue life is eliminated. This implies that it should be possible to predict fatigue lifetimes of impact damaged composites from knowledge of the residual strength of the impact damaged composite and the S–N curve for the undamaged material.

In conclusion, lifetime of damaged specimens can be estimated according to the S–N curve of undamaged one, with the residual strength. So it is not needed to do fatigue tests on damaged specimens. The diagram is described in Fig. 4. According to the proposed approach, for simple case, a safety factor can be defined as ratio of strength / residual strength.

Figure 4: Diagram of proposed approach

4 NUMERICAL SIMULATION ANALYSIS

Following to the previous descriptions, the study of ballast impact influence on fatigue assessment can be realized with four point bending test. All numerical simulations (using ABAQUS/Explicit) can be divided into two parts: bending before impact; impact and bending after impact.

For validating a numerical model, an arbitrary composite material is chosen for the finite element analysis. The mechanical properties are presented in Table 2. The plate is modelled as quasi-isotropic structure with stacking sequence: [(45/-45/0/90)₂]_s.

Elastic properties		Damage properties	
<i>Composite material modelling (T800S/M21)</i>			
Density ρ (g/cm ³)	1.58	Longitudinal tensile strength X_t (MPa)	3039
Young's modulus E_1 (GPa)	172	Longitudinal compressive strength X_c (MPa)	1669
Young's modulus E_2 (GPa)	10	Transverse tensile strength Y_t (MPa)	50
Shear modulus G_{12} (GPa)	5	Transverse compressive strength Y_c (MPa)	250
Poisson's ratio ν_{12} (-)	0.3	Shear strength $S_{L,T}$ (MPa)	79
		Shear interaction factor α	0
		Fracture energy fibre tension $G_{C,Xt}$ (kJ/m ²)	150
		Fracture energy fibre compr. $G_{C,Xc}$ (kJ/m ²)	75
		Fracture energy matrix tension $G_{C,Yt}$ (kJ/m ²)	2
		Fracture energy matrix compr. $G_{C,Yc}$ (kJ/m ²)	25
<i>Delamination modelling (T800S/M21)</i>			
Interface stiffness K_{nn} (GPa/mm)	1	Maximum normal traction t_{n0} (GPa)	0.02
Interface stiffness $K_{ss} = K_{tt}$ (GPa/mm)	2	Maximum shear traction $t_{s0} = t_{t0}$ (GPa)	0.08
		Critical energy release rate mode I G_{IC} (J/m ²)	512
		Critical energy release rate mode II G_{IIc} (J/m ²)	2000

Table 2: Material parameters used for the numerical simulations [16]

A French standard [23] describes a method of test to simulate ballast impact (Fig. 5). This test consists in launching an impactor, simulating stone ballast on different parts of train structure to assess its impact strength. In the following numerical model, the same shape of impactor is used. The mass of the projectile is 0.06 kg.

A numerical model is created using ABAQUS/CAE. The composite laminate has dimensions 150 mm x 100 mm with a thickness of 5.0 mm (16 plies). The composite plate is discretized with the help of continuum shell element SC8R. The cohesive elements of type COH3D8 (zero thickness) are applied between all plies to simulate inter-laminar damages (15 interfaces). An element size of 1.25 mm is chosen for the impact zone of this model. Cylinders and impactor are simulated by analytical rigid surface. Hashin's failure criteria are used for prediction of damage initiation and evolution of intra-laminar damages. The initiation of inter-laminar damages (delaminations) is predicted using QUADS damage criterion and their evolution is modelled by B-K criterion with $\eta = 1.45$.

Figure 5: Dimensions of impactor [23] - (in mm)

4.1 Bending before impact

The numerical model for four point bending test is presented in Fig. 6. Distance between two upper cylinders is 60 mm. For the lower supports (cylinders), this value is 120 mm.

According to obtained results on the unimpacted specimen, a displacement vs. loading curve is illustrated in Fig. 7.

Figure 6: Numerical model under bending test

Figure 7: Displacement vs. loading curve

4.2 Impact and bending

Stage 1: Impact

Based on a literature review (experimental and numerical results), the variables in following have been analyzed frequently:

- Impact force time history,
- Impact energy time history,
- Force vs. displacement curve,
- Deflection vs. impact energy curve,
- Absorbed energy vs. impact energy curve.
- Etc.

Generally, the above results could be obtained easily in comparison to damage inspection and simulation. In particular, delamination areas are considered as a reference parameter for evaluating damage level.

According to ASTM standard D7136, the composite plate is totally clamped (Fig. 8). As an example, the results of an impact of 3J are presented.

Figure 8: Impact model

- Intra-laminar damages

The Hashin damage model is primarily intended for use with fiber-reinforced composite materials and takes into account four different failure modes: fiber tension, fiber compression, matrix tension, and matrix compression.

With necessary output setting, all plies can be analyzed respectively (ply by ply). The composite plies and the interfaces are numbered from bottom to top (the 16th ply is the top ply in contact with the impactor). As an example, each type of damage of the 16th ply is respectively illustrated in Fig. 9-12 as follows:

Figure 9: Fiber tensile damage in the 16th ply (top ply)

Figure 10: Fiber compressive damage in the 16th ply (top ply)

Figure 11: Matrix tensile damage in the 16th ply (top ply)

Figure 12: Matrix compressive damage in the 16th ply (top ply)

- Inter-laminar damages (delamination)

For better understanding delamination distribution, damaged area of the 15th interface is presented in Fig. 13. The cohesive elements can be deleted automatically when value of SDEG (Scalar stiffness degradation at integration points) reaches a value of one.

Figure 13: Delamination distribution in the 15th interfaces

Stage 2: Bending after impact

A bending test simulation is realized after impact. The numerical model is shown in Fig. 14.

Figure 14: Bending after impact

Based on obtained results of the impacted specimen, a displacement vs. loading curve is illustrated in Fig. 15. A significant difference on strength can be observed.

Figure 15: Comparison between before impact and after impact

According to the proposed approach, a safety factor can be calculated as follows (Eq. 5):

$$\text{Safety factor} = \frac{\text{strength}}{\text{residual strength}} \quad (5)$$

In conclusion, for the previous case (impact of 3J), the safety factor is equal to 1.07.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Ballast impact problems are quite frequently encountered by rolling stock manufacturers and this type of impact cannot be avoided. In order to predict the ballast impact influence, a finite element (FE) model that is carefully developed can accurately predict in relatively short time the complex internal damage pattern that is formed in composite laminates when subjected to impact loading.

Finite element method is applied to ballast impact analysis by using ABAQUS/Explicit. Many impact parameters have been considered in the numerical model, such as: impactor shape, mass, velocity; material properties of composite plate and its stacking sequences; etc. After validation of numerical models, impact behaviour, resistance of undamaged specimens and residual resistance of damaged specimens under 4 point bending have been simulated, respectively.

Based on a literature review, an approach for evaluating ballast impact influence in fatigue assessment has been proposed. Lifetime of damaged specimens can be estimated according to the S-N curve of undamaged one, with the residual strength. A safety factor can be defined as ratio of strength / residual strength.

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